

FINANCIAL STATEMENT ANALYSIS USING COMMON SIZE ON MAHINDRA SINDOL MOTORS

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ABSTRACT

A Primary limitation of the typical economic statements comprising the balance sheet and the earnings and loss account is that they do not supply all the information related to the monetary operation of a firm. Nevertheless ,they furnish some extra ordinarily useful information to the extent that the balance sheet mirrors the economic position on a precise date in terms of the structure of the assets, liabilities and owners, equity, and so on and the earnings and loss account shows the outcomes of operation at some stage in a certain length of time in terms of the revenues acquired and the cost incurred at some point of the year . Thus, the financial statements supply a summarized view of the financial function and operations of a firm. Therefore, a good deal can be learnt about a company from a careful examination of its economic statements as valuable documents/performance reports. The analysis of financial statements is, thus, an vital aid to financial analysis.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The main aim of marketing is meet and satisfy target customer need and buyers behaviour refers to people or organisation conduct activities and together with the impact of various influence on them towards making decision on purchase of product and service in a market.

The field of consumer behaviour studies how individuals ,groups and organisation selects,buy, use and dispose of good, service, ideas, or experience to satisfy their needs and desires understanding consumer behaviour and knowing customer are never simple .They are responding to influences that changes their mind at the last minute. A buyer makes takes a decision whether save or spends the money.

Mahindra And Mahindra started a joint venture with British Telecom in 1986 as a technology outsourcing firm. British Telecom initially had around 30 Percentage stake in the MAHINDRA AND MAHINDRA company . In December 2010, British Telecom sold

5.5 Percent of its stake In Tech Mahindra to Mahindra and Mahindra for Rs 451 crore .In August 2012, British Telecom sold 14.1 Percent of its stake to institutional investors for about Rs 1,395 crore . In December 2012, British telecom sold its remaining 9.1 Percent (11.6 million shares) shareholding to institutional investors, for a total gross cash proceeds of Rs 1,011.4 crore .This sale marked

OUR CORE VALUES

We, at Mahindra, are driven by a single purpose – to RISE! We mean and intend to rise Beyond doubts, fear and skepticism; for ourselves, for our family and our nation. In Pursuit of outperforming our own standards, we relentlessly work towards achieving Excellence, covering as many industries as we can, satisfying as many customers as we can And most importantly touching as many lives as we can.

OUR LEADERSHIP

Mahindra's leaders set the tone and lead the charge in our aspiration to be one of the world's 50 most admired global brands by 2021. They direct our focus on technology and innovation, Chart our global expansion, and lay the markers for our growth Our leadership's ability to manage our operations and finances the world over, build and Groom our global talent pool, and lead our endeavours in new markets and geographies help To constantly move forward and offer our customers only the very best .

2.1 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The focus of economic analysis is on key figures in the economic statements and the widespread relationship that exist between them. The evaluation of economic statements is a system of appreciation of the firm's role and performance. The first project of the economic analyst is to choose the data applicable to the choice under consideration from the complete records contained in the financial statements. The 2nd step is to organize the data in a way to

spotlight massive relationships. The ultimate step is interpretation and drawing of inferences and conclusions. In quick financial evaluation is the method of selection, relation and evaluation.

Common size statement:

Common dimension assertion express property and liabilities as percentage of whole property and fees and earnings as percentage of sales. Common –size comparative statements prepared for one association over the years would spotlight the relative modification in every group of expenses, belongings and liabilities. These statement can be equally useful for inter-firm comparable, given the facts that absolute figures of two firms of the identical enterprise are no longer comparable.

3. REASEARCH DESIGN

3.1 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The technology of globalization modern-day free market economic system introduce a window of company acidity that has large effect on any countries trade and general development. To whole the process of company or trading monetary intermediaries and group act like as safe gateway between two sides. As an institution, company has been contributing towards the improvement of any economy for a long time and at the moment it is dealt with as an essential company enterprise in modern world. Now days the functioning vicinity of company now not costrained within equal geographical restrict of any country.

3.2 NEED FOR THE STUDY

The economic statements are reflecting which reflects the financial function and electricity or weak point of the concern. The company monetary agency has been witnessed severe opposition from company and global company. Every business wants to economic performance analysis.

The find out about on monetary overall performance frequent measurement of Mahindra & Mahindra is conducted to measure the universal overall performance of the company. The economic evaluation strengths the association to make their excellent use, and to be in a position to spot out economic weakness of the company to country appropriate corrective actions.

3.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- It is beneficial in comparing two or more periods or two or more companies when the productive capacity is not the same.
- The comparative significance of each individual item of expenses and incomes stands out clearly.
- A study of common size percentage of a company indicates the structure of profit and loss account.
- The common size income statement also shows the distribution of profit in form of interest, taxes and dividends.
- To understand the concept of financial performance.
- From the viewpoint of researcher the above objectives depend on accuracy, quality, quantity and availability of data regarding financial information.

3.4 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study is based on the accounting information of the Mahindra Sindol motors, Bidar. The study covers the period of 2015-2017 for analysing the financial statement such as profit and loss account and balance sheet.

The scope of the study involves the various factors that affect the financial efficiency of the company. To increase the profit and growth of the company.

The data of the past three years are taken into account for the study. The performance is compared within those periods.

3.5 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research can be defined as “A Scientific and systemic search for pertinent records on a unique topic”. Therefore, research should be understood as a geared up pastime with particular targets on a hassle or issues supported through compilation of associated facts and facts, involving utility of relevant equipment of evaluation and deriving logically on originality.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Research Design is the arrangement of condition for collection and evaluation of statistics in manner that aims to combine relevance to the research reason with the economy in procedure. Research Design is necessary notably due to the fact of the expanded complexity in the market as well as advertising and marketing techniques on hand to the researchers.

SOURCES OF DATA

- PRIMARY DATA
- SECONDRY DATA

4.DATA AND ANALYSIS

FINANCIAL STATEMENT ANALYSIS COMMON SIZE PROFIT AND LOSS ACCOUNT OF MAHINDRA SINDOL MOTORS

	2017	%2017	2016	%2016	2015	%2015
Revenue	29,141	100	26,494	100	22,621	100
Employee cost	15,454	53.03	13,908	52.49	11,914	52.66
other cost	9503	32.61	8268	31.20	6516	28.80
Depreciation	978	3.35	762	2.87	611	2.70
Interest expenses	129	0.44	96	0.36	69	0.30
Taxes	1002	3.44	860	3.24	960	4.24
Net profit	2813	9.65	3118	11.76	2628	11.61

FINANCIAL STATEMENT ANALYSIS COMMON SIZE BALANCE SHEET OF MAHINDRA SINDOL MOTORS

(RS. Crores)

	2017	%2017	2016	%2016	2015	%2015
Share Capital	297.06	1.00	296.32	1..22	295.70	1.35
Reserves & Surplus	26488.56	89.61	22126.85	91.18	18948.60	86.62
Net Worth	26785.62	90.61	22423.17	92.40	19255.09	88.02
Secured Loan	12.20	0.04	.00	00	.00	00
Unsecured Loan	2760.67	9.34	1843.55	7.60	2620.38	11.98
TOTAL LIABILITIES	29558.49	100	24266.72	100	21875.47	100
Assets						

Gross Block	14501.88	49.06	13241.17	54.56	11109.91	50.78
(-) Acc. Depreciation	6730.84	22.77	5645.18	23.26	5180.45	23.68
Net Block	7771.04	26.29	7595.99	31.30	5918.67	27.05
Capital Work in Progress	2040.40	6.90	1562.15	6.43	2178.76	9.95
Investments	17908.40	60.58	13547.40	55.82	13138.16	60.05
Inventories	2758.01	9.33	2687.93	11.07	2437.57	11.14
Sundry Debtors	2938.84	9.94	2511.64	10.35	2558.03	11.69
Cash and Bank	1687.48	5.70	2287.03	9.42	2064.77	9.43
Loans and Advances	4864.15	16.45	5307.43	21.87	4638.12	21.20
Total Current Assets	12248.48	41.43	12794.03	52.72	11698.49	53.47
Current Liabilities	9019.90	30.51	10168.07	41.90	9000.62	41.14
Provisions	1389.93	4.70	1064.78	4.38	2068.78	9.45
Total Current Liabilities	10409.83	35.21	11232.85	46.28	11069.40	50.60
NET CURRENT ASSETS	1838.65	6.22	1561.18	6.43	629.09	2.87
TOTAL						
ASSETS(A+B+C+D+E)	29558.49	100	24266.72	100	21875.47	100

4.1 ANALYSIS OF EMPLOYEES COST?

Employees Cost	Amount	% Common Size
2015	11914	52.66
2016	13908	52.49
2017	15454	53.03

Interpretation:

The above table and graph shown that Common Size of Employees Cost in the year 2015 is 52.66, 2016 is 52.49 and 2017 is 53.03

4.2 ANALYSIS OF OTHER COST?

Other Cost	Amount	% Common Size
2015	6516	28.80
2016	8268	31.20
2017	9503	32.61

Interpretation:

The above table and graph shown that Common Size of Other Cost in the year 2015 is 28.80,2016 is 31.20 and 2017 is 32.61

4.3 ANALYSIS OF DEPRECIATION?

Depreciation	Amount	% Common Size
2015	611	2.70
2016	762	2.87
2017	978	3.35

Interpretation:

The above table and graph shown that Common Size of Depreciation in the year 2015 is 2.70,2016 is 2.87 and 2017 is 3.35.

4.4 ANALYSIS OF INTEREST EXPENSES?

Interest Expenses	Amount	% Common Size
2015	129	0.44
2016	96	0.36
2017	69	0.30

Interpretation:

The above table and graph shown that Common Size of Interest Expenses in the year 2015 is 0.44, 2016 is 0.36 and 2017 is 0.30.

4.5 ANALYSIS OF TAXES?

Taxes	Amount	% Common Size
2015	960	4.24
2016	860	3.24
2017	1002	3.44

Interpretation:

The above table and graph shown that Common Size of Taxes in the year 2015 is 4.24, 2016 is 3.24 and 2017 is 3.44.

4.6 ANALYSIS OF NET PROFIT?

Net Profit	Amount	% Common Size
2015	2628	11.61
2016	3118	11.76
2017	2813	9.65

Interpretation:

The above table and graph shown that Common Size of Net Profit in the year 2015 is 11.61, 2016 is 11.76 and 2017 is 9.65.

4.7 ANALYSIS OF NET WORTH?

Net Worth	Amount	% Common Size
2015	19255.09	88.02
2016	22423.17	92.40
2017	26785.62	90.61

Interpretation:

The above table and graph shown that Common Size of Net Worth in the year 2015 is 88.02,2016 is 92.40 and 2017 is 90.61.

4.8 ANALYSIS OF SECURED LOAN?

Secured Loan	Amount	% Common Size
2015	00	0.00
2016	00	0.00
2017	12.20	0.04

Interpretation:

The above table and graph shown that Common Size of Secured Loan in the year 2015 is 0.00,2016 is 0.00 and 2017 is 0.04.

4.9 ANALYSIS OF UNSECURED LOAN?

Unsecured Loan	Amount	% Common Size
2015	2620.38	11.98
2016	1843.55	7.60
2017	2760.67	9.34

Interpretation:

The above table and graph shown that Common Size of Unsecured Loan in the year 2015 is 11.98,2016 is 7.60 and 2017 is 9.34.

4.10 ANALYSIS OF NET BLOCK?

Net Block	Amount	% Common Size
2015	5918.67	27.05
2016	7595.99	31.30
2017	7771.04	26.29

Interpretation:

The above table and graph shown that Common Size of Net Block in the year 2015 is 27.05,2016 is 31.30 and 2017 is 26.29.

4.11 ANALYSIS OF INVESTMENTS?

Investments	Amount	% Common Size
2015	13138.16	60.05
2016	13547.40	55.82
2017	17908.40	60.58

Interpretation:

The above table and graph shown that Common Size of Investments in the year 2015 is 60.05, 2016 is 55.82 and 2017 is 60.58.

4.12 ANALYSIS OF LOANS AND ADVANCES?

Loans and Advances	Amount	% Common Size
2015	4638.12	21.20
2016	5307.43	21.87
2017	4864.15	16.45

Interpretation:

The above table and graph shown that Common Size of Loans and Advances in the year 2015 is 21.20, 2016 is 21.87 and 2017 is 16.45.

5. FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

5.1 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

- It is observed that the activity expended of the company is low related to final 12 months pastime expended by means of the company.
- It is determined that the running expenses of the financial statement is high with related to the remaining year of working charges of the company
- It is found that the provision and contingencies of the financial statement is low with related to the remaining 12 months of provision and contingencies of the company.
- It is found that the total income of the company is high with associated to the final year of complete revenue of the company.

5.2 CONCLUSION

Company Financial statement over the years has been more than a few companies. Today Indian company is below reform process. Foreign company are entering into market and private companies gaining momentum. This stage is crucial for nationalized companies like Mahindra & Mahindra. Its future depends on how it can face threats and cash on opportunities. Thinking globally considering local aspects is the need of this hour. M & M financial statement has to use its tremendous company journey to reap a robust preserve in the Indian company system and build a globally respected brand. M & M has a brilliant future as it gives higher thrust towards technological up gradation of its operation beside this, the financial statement has additionally hooked up. Realizing and evolving the various needs of clients the financial statement has various too, getting into several new areas such as service provider company, hire buy and leasing and digital remittance provider etc.

5.3 SUGGESTION / RECOMMENDATIONS

In order to improve their monetary performance, the M&M financial statement is advised the following based on the analysis.

- The financial statement must inspire and impart proper know-how about company to their staff.

- The company should carry new products/ services based on the aspirations of customers.
- The financial statement need to become more clients centric by using leveraging sophisticated insights to enhance hazard administration pricing, channel overall performance and consumer satisfaction.

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